

LEX HUMANITARIAE: JOURNAL FOR A CHANGE (ISSN: 2582-5216)

**VOLUME I ISSUE II
APRIL 2020**

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ARBITRATION & CONCILIATION (AMENDMENT) BILL 2019 - AN OPINION VIS-À-VIS INTERNATIONAL ARBITRATION

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ABSTRACT

The article is a legislative comment on the Arbitration & Conciliation (Amendment) Bill introduced in 2019 keeping in mind Arbitration in the International context and comparing it with the Amendment Act and the Legislature in Indian context.

The new 2019 amendment, envisages major changes which will be discussed in this Article vis-à-vis International Arbitration. The article critically analyzes some of its provisions to understand if it is indeed a step in the right direction for India to become a hub for international arbitration. The analysis and comments in this article are solely and exclusively from the standpoint of international arbitration.

Thus, the Arbitration and Conciliation Act in India needs to be looked at in reference to both international and principles of Indian law. The uncertainty would arise mainly in context of the rules which the parties frame in the course of arbitration, which have not been codified. Thus, this practice must be examined in light of the UNCITRAL rules and Indian Administrative law, (since the Arbitration Tribunal is a quasi-judicial body) and it should then be seen whether the manner of framing rules under the Arbitration Act is as envisaged under the UNCITRAL model law.

INTRODUCTION

Alternate Dispute Resolution, as the name itself suggests, is the resolution of a dispute through means other than courts and the orthodox legal systems like litigation. As discussed earlier, Alternate Dispute Resolution merely aims to solve a dispute that is very small in context to a conflict. It aims to solve the dispute through ways that are agreeable to both parties mostly through compromise so that the feeling of winner-loser does not apprise them. In sharp contrast to conventional court rules where one party wins and one loses, thus in the way of justice, in turn, it starts a new grudge from the loser to the winner, which in the long run is harmful to the international community of member nations of the world.

The word ‘dispute’ means ‘disagreement,’ and the word ‘resolution’ means “the action of solving something.” Alternate dispute resolution is a form of agreement Alternative Dispute Resolution includes substitute methods of helping people to resolve legal problems before going to court or as directed by the court. In ADR, “neutral” is an independent third person who tries to help resolve the areas of conflict or at least narrow it down.

After India opened up its borders there was greater need for a quick disposal of cases which the judiciary could not provide and this would hamper trade. Thus a new private sector of alternate dispute resolution was projected through arbitration for better disposal of cases where each case would be solved in a manner tailor-made for the peculiar problem. The existing law relating to international arbitration was considered archaic and outdated and various sectors demanded its overhaul. Accordingly, in 1995, the Minister for Law, Justice and Company Affairs introduced in the Upper House of Parliament the Rajya Sabha, a Bill to implement the UNCITRAL Model Law and also to

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provide statutory recognition to the process of conciliation. Thus, the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 was enacted.

Alternate Dispute Resolution customarily includes mediation, arbitration, negotiation, early neutral evaluation, and conciliation. Nations have begun experimenting with ADR programs as rising costs of litigation, time delays, and burgeoning court queues continue to plague litigants. Some of these ADR programs initiated by the states are voluntary; others are mandatory.

UNCITRAL MODEL LAW

The Model Law is designed to meet concerns relating to the current state of national laws on arbitration. The need for improvement and harmonization is based on findings that domestic laws are often inappropriate for international cases and that considerable disparity exists between them. The principles and individual solutions adopted in the Model Law aim at reducing or eliminating the above concerns and difficulties. As a response to the inadequacies and disparities of national laws, the Model Law presents a special legal regime geared to international commercial arbitration, without affecting any relevant treaty in force in the State adopting the Model Law. While the need for uniformity exists only in respect of international cases, the desire of updating and improving the arbitration law may be felt by a State also in respect of non-international cases and could be met by enacting modern legislation based on the Model Law for both categories of cases.

THE INDIAN ARBITRATION ACT

The Indian Arbitration Act corresponds to the UNCITRAL model rules of arbitration and was actually enacted as a result of India signing the UNCITRAL treaty on arbitration and the recommendation flowing from the UNCITRAL that all countries signing it try to give due consideration to the arbitration rules framed under the model law. It has various similarities with the above rules which were framed for the purpose of gaining uniformity in the rules while referring to disputes which arise in the context of international commercial relations and where the parties wish to settle the dispute amicably.

The Preamble to the Indian Arbitration Act shows that the object of the Act is to consolidate and amend the law relating to arbitration in India. The law in India is thus based largely on the UNCITRAL model law of arbitration. However, the law must follow not only the principles laid down by the United Nations on arbitration but also all the principles of Indian law including the general principles of Constitutional and Administrative law.

THE AMENDMENT

The Arbitration & Conciliation (Amendment) Act, 2019, amending the Indian Arbitration & Conciliation Act, 1996, entered into force with effect from 9 August 2019. The Indian Minister of Law was quoted in one of the press releases recently to say that by bringing changes to legislation in order to resolve commercial disputes the government was intended to make India a hub for domestic and international arbitrations.

The new 2019 amendment, envisages major changes which will be discussed in this Article vis-à-vis International Arbitration. The article critically analyzes some of its provisions to understand if it is indeed a step in the right direction for India to become a hub for international arbitration. The analysis and comments in this article are solely and exclusively from the standpoint of international arbitration.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE 2019 AMENDMENT'S KEY PROVISIONS

The designation and grading of arbitral institutions

The 2019 amendment adds Part 1A to the Act, called 'India's Arbitration Council,' which empowers the central government to set up the ACI. The amendment act also sets out in Section 43C(1)(a) to (f) a comprehensive constitution of the ACI. Among other things, the ACI is responsible for classifying arbitral institutions on the basis of criteria relating to infrastructure, quality and arbitrator caliber, performance and compliance with time limits for disposal of domestic or international commercial arbitration (Section 43I)

The main disadvantage of the arrangement is that it restricts party sovereignty through intervention by government and the court in international arbitration. The ACI is a governmental body that regulates the institutionalization and classification of arbitration in India. The fact remains that the decision of the court to select an arbitral tribunal would be limited by the ACI's choices. The selection of a third parties appealing before the Supreme Court for appointment of an arbitrator shall therefore be limited to ACI accredited institutions and to those arbitrators who may be on the panel of the arbitral institutions concerned. In designating an ungraduated institution that has an global reputation for its facilities and services quality and which actually wants to set up its local office in India, the court will be similarly handicapped without going through administrative hurdles of being assessed by the ACI.

Although the 2019 amendment seeks to institutionalize the arbitration scene in India, it leaves the courts and the executive's discretion to decide who is to participate in the change. The (possible) nepotism, red-tapism, lack of objectivity, and lack of transparency in the rating process are also associated with this control of institutionalization by the government. Throughout my experience, a foreign party frequently prefers to stay away from a scheme of court or government arbitration with significant intervention. Nevertheless, the government is happy to accept that international arbitration is the only way forward to bring foreign parties into its arbitration agreements to include India as the location.

Confidentiality

Under the newly introduced Section 42A, if its divulgation is required for the application and compliance of an award, the arbitrator, the arbitrator and the parties to the arbitration agreement shall remain confidential in every arbitral procedure except award. The ICC has recently published updates of its Note to Contracting Parties and discretionary tribunals on the conduct of arbitration in compliance with the ICC rules, effective 1 January 2019, whereby it has specified that, not less than two years after notification of the awards given on 1 January 2019, it may be published by opt-out proceedings (paras. 40-46). Any party may at any time object to the publication of an award under the opt-out process, or request that the award be sanitized or written out. In this case the award is either not issued, sanitized or written in compliance with the agreement of the parties.

This at the outset indicates that India's approach in the development of the award conforms to the arbitral institutions of the world. However, the legislative authority missed the opportunity of clarifying the fate of an award with regard to its publication, by not integrating an opt-out in Section 42A. Who is going to decide that an award must be revealed to be carried out? Are parties required to decide on a written contract, does it require full disclosure? In my opinion, these complexities add to the suspense.

Qualification of arbitrators

The ACI is also responsible for evaluating the arbitrators ' rating (Section 43D(2)(c)). As provided for in Amendment 2019 (Section 43J), the credentials, expertise and levels of accreditation of arbitrators will be as defined in Schedule 8. The Eighth Schedule stipulates nine categories, and only those who

are eligible to be arbitratory, (for example, an Indian lawyer, cost accountant, business secretary of a certain level of experience or governmental official in some cases).

As a result, the tribunal under the 2019 Amendment shall be excluded as a foreign scholar or an overseas licensed lawyer or retired foreign officer. International parties will be deterred from opting for Indian institutional Arbitration, where choices of applicants as their future arbitrators are constrained by ethnicity, possibility and expertise in the handling of international arbitration—both academic and vocational.

Timely conduct of proceedings

In compliance with newly introduced Section 23(5), a statement of claim shall be concluded and an international commercial arbitration award shall be submitted as quickly as possible within six months from the appointment of the arbitrator(s) and in accordance with Proviso to amended Section 29(1), with an attempt to offer such award within 12 months of the date of the completion

While it is an appropriate move, with definitely a good intention, the rule of an arbitral institution that clash, as it overlooks the procedural aspects of complex international arbitration. Under international arbitration, the arbitrators hold a case management hearing regularly and issue a procedure schedule for the completion of pleadings and the execution of hearings after consulting the parties. If, however, Article 23(4) restricts the court to monitor its proceedings, complex multi-party arbitrations involving large-scale documents may be unable to carry out efficiently if it could be virtually impossible in six months to complete pleadings. In the same way, parties are severely limited in their discretion to agree on a more flexible procedure plan. Above all they will always be worried about the fate of an award where Section 23(4) does not stick to the time requirements strictly.

Arbitral Immunity

The 2019 bill proposes that arbitrators should be immune from prosecution or other legal proceedings for anything done in good faith, or planned to do in compliance with the A&C Act or its laws. The amendment introduced in this respect is in accordance with current standards. For example, in Singapore, in the sense of the arbitration proceedings or in the making of the Arbitration Award the arbitrator shall not be held liable for incompetence as an arbitrator and error in law, reality or method.

Applicability of 2015 Amendments

The 2019 Bill proposes to define the procedure to be followed by the modifications introduced by the amendment act. The bill for 2019 is intended to remove Section 26 of the Amendments Act and clarify that the Amendments Act only applies to arbitration proceedings begun on or after 23 October 2015, and to those proceedings resulting from such arbitral proceedings.

The 2019 bill tries in this way to overturn a recent Supreme Court decision on the issue of 'Cricket Board of Control for India c. Kochi Cricket Pvt. Ltd.' In the above case, the Supreme Court held that Section 26 would be applicable to arbitrations and judicial proceedings starting after 23 October 2015. It has also established that, in the event of an automatic stay on the implementation of award pursuant to submission of an application for set aside which plagues arbitration, amended Section 36 would extend to all proceedings. In the face of thousands of proceedings throughout the country—many at a very advanced stage—and in response to the Supreme Court ruling the amendment law is at risk of chaos in an intent for changing the application of the Amendment Act. For example, cases that have followed the decision of the Supreme Court and are now in the process of enforcement may be stopped. Such a change does not well match the goals of consistency and predictability and actually adds to the challenge found in the arbitration process.

CONCLUSION

India frequently criticized the international community's "non-friendly" arbitration body. The 2019 Amendment attempts to take this criticism head-on, but in my opinion, in the process, it makes more mistakes than hits. Even though India is still a step in the right direction, it is far from becoming a global centre of arbitration.